

Synthesis, crystallographic characterization and DNA binding properties of a manganese(II) complex containing 1,10-phenanthroline ligand

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Abstract : A mononuclear manganese(II) complex $[\text{Mn}(\text{phen})_2(\text{OH}_2)_2][\text{Mn}(\text{phen})_2(\text{OH}_2)\text{Cl}](\text{NO}_3)_3$ (**1**) containing 1,10-phenanthroline [phen=1,10-phenanthroline] ligand has been synthesized and crystallographically characterized. The oxidation level of the manganese atoms in two asymmetric units was determined by bond valence sum calculation (BVS). The DNA binding study has been explored by spectrophotometric and spectrofluorimetric measurements.

Keywords : Manganese(II), BVS calculation, supramolecular interaction, DNA binding study.

Introduction

Synthesis of small synthetic systems that recognize specific sites of DNA is an important area of much current research¹⁻³. The factors that determine the affinity and selectivity in binding small molecules to DNA would be valuable in the rational design of new diagnostic and therapeutic agents³⁻⁶. Many times, such physical complexation may produce important pharmacological effects by interfering with the biological processes in which DNA/RNAs take part. Such investigations also sometimes provide insights for the mechanism of action of naturally occurring antitumor antibiotics⁷. The interaction of transition metal complexes with DNA has attracted much attention during past few decades. The metal complexes can interact non-covalently with nucleic acids by intercalation when the ligand contains planar ring systems, groove binding for large molecules, or external electrostatic binding for cations. The binding modes are dependent on the sizes and stereochemical properties of the metal complexes. 1,10-Phenanthroline ligands have been extensively utilized for the complexation of metal cations, particularly those of *d* and *f* blocks. Due to the sound combination of some distinct structural and chemical properties, manganese complexes with phenanthroline ligands have been actively studied since the seventies for their cata-

lytic, redox and photophysical properties⁸⁻¹⁰. Here, we investigate the details of synthetic, molecular and supramolecular structural networks and DNA binding study of the manganese(II) complex.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and formulation :

The mononuclear complex was prepared from chloride salt of manganese(II) with symmetrical bidentate blockers (phen) and ammonium ceric nitrate (CAN) in 1 : 2 : 1 molar ratio in saturated methanolic solution of sodium acetate for at room temperature.

The schematic presentation of syntheses is given below :

Sat. NaOAc in MeOH

The complex is sufficiently stable in air and in presence of moisture. The compound **1** is soluble in almost all solvents like methanol, ethanol, dichloromethane, acetonitrile and dimethyl formamide (DMF). The complex was characterized by spectroscopy and single-crystal X-ray

crystallography. In IR spectra, the point of interest in the compound is well resolved peaks at $\sim 3418\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to O–H stretch of coordinated water molecules¹¹. The high intense peak at 1384 cm^{-1} indicates the presence of counter anionic NO_3^- . The compound show relatively intense peaks around $1588\text{--}1610\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the C=N stretching frequency and weak bands in the range $2980\text{--}2900\text{ cm}^{-1}$ due to the aliphatic C–H stretching frequency.

Crystal structure :

An Oak Ridge Thermal Ellipsoid Plot (ORTEP) with atom numbering scheme of the mononuclear complex **1** is shown in Fig. 1. Selected bond angles and bond lengths relevant to the coordination sphere are listed in Table 2. Single crystal structural analysis reveals that crystal lattice of **1** contains two unsymmetrical independent $[\text{Mn}(\text{phen})_2(\text{OH}_2)\text{Cl}]^+$ and $[\text{Mn}(\text{phen})_2(\text{OH}_2)_2]^{2+}$ cationic units and three NO_3^- anions. Though the two cationic units in the lattice exist independently, but each of the manganese is in +2 oxidation state. This crystallographic experimental fact is in good agreement with Bond Valence Sum calculation¹².

Parameters	1
Empirical formula	$\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_{11}\text{ClO}_{12}\text{Mn}_2$
Formula weight	1105.17
Temperature (K)	296(2)
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	P21(4)
<i>a</i> (Å)	9.0654(7)
<i>b</i> (Å)	13.8364(10)
<i>c</i> (Å)	19.6614(14)
Volume (Å ³)	2408.0(3)
<i>Z</i>	2
ρ (g cm ⁻³)	1.569
μ (mm ⁻¹)	0.712
<i>F</i> (000)	1158
θ ranges (°)	1.1–31.4
<i>R</i> _{int}	0.035
<i>R</i> (reflections)	37879
<i>wR</i> ₂ (reflections)	13683
Final <i>R</i> indices	0.0576, 0.1807

Fig. 1. ORTEP representation of **1** with 20% thermal ellipsoid probability.

Table 2. Selected bond distances (Å) and angles (°) for **1**

Bond distances :			
Mn(1)-N(3)	2.261(4)	Mn(1)-N(6)	2.259(4)
Mn(1)-N(4)	2.298(4)	Mn(1)-O(16)	2.140(4)
Mn(1)-N(5)	2.245(4)	Mn(1)-O(87)	2.206(3)
Mn(2)-N(1)	2.282(4)	Mn(2)-N(8)	2.259(4)
Mn(2)-N(2)	2.251(4)	Mn(2)-O(15)	2.187(3)
Mn(2)-N(7)	2.242(4)	Mn(2)-Cl(1)	2.4726(12)
Bond angles :			
N(1)-Mn(2)-N(2)	73.10(14)	N(3)-Mn(1)-N(4)	73.50(13)
N(1)-Mn(2)-N(7)	96.72(14)	N(3)-Mn(1)-N(5)	98.70(13)
N(1)-Mn(2)-N(8)	90.09(14)	N(3)-Mn(1)-N(6)	160.62(15)
N(2)-Mn(2)-N(7)	98.65(14)	N(4)-Mn(1)-N(5)	97.74(14)
N(2)-Mn(2)-N(8)	161.21(15)	N(4)-Mn(1)-N(6)	89.26(13)
N(7)-Mn(2)-N(8)	74.54(13)	N(5)-Mn(1)-N(6)	74.45(13)
Cl(1)-Mn(2)-N(1)	89.55(10)	O(16)-Mn(1)-N(3)	91.36(14)
Cl(1)-Mn(2)-N(2)	94.92(10)	O(16)-Mn(1)-N(4)	164.37(13)
Cl(1)-Mn(2)-N(8)	93.24(10)	O(16)-Mn(1)-N(5)	88.17(14)
Cl(1)-Mn(2)-O(15)	90.56(7)	O(16)-Mn(1)-N(6)	106.29(13)
Cl(1)-Mn(2)-N(7)	166.21(10)	O(87)-Mn(1)-N(3)	94.49(12)
O(15)-Mn(2)-N(1)	163.89(12)	O(87)-Mn(1)-N(4)	87.90(12)
O(15)-Mn(2)-N(2)	90.85(12)	O(87)-Mn(1)-N(5)	166.6(12)
O(15)-Mn(2)-N(7)	86.80(12)	O(87)-Mn(1)-N(6)	93.63(12)
O(15)-Mn(2)-N(8)	105.98(12)	O(87)-Mn(1)-O(16)	89.52(12)

The coordination geometry of Mn atoms in each asymmetric centre is best described as distorted octahedron. The Mn1-N/O and Mn2-N/O/Cl distances are in the range 2.140(4)–2.298(4) Å and 2.187(3)–2.4726(12) Å, respectively. The difference between the shortest and the longest Mn1-N/O and Mn2-N/O/Cl bond Δ amounts 0.158/0.2856 Å. Close inspection of the bond angle and bond distance data of Mn1 and Mn2 coordination environment in **1** suggests that N5 and O87 occupy the axial positions (\angle N5-Mn1-O87 = 166.6) and N7, Cl1 (\angle N7-Mn2-Cl1 = 166.2) occupy the axial positions of the distorted octahedron respectively. The bond angles O(16)-Mn(1)-O(87) and Cl(1)-Mn(2)-O(15) as 89.52(12)° and 90.56(7)° in two asymmetric units around Mn1 and Mn2 centre indicate the *cisoid* representation of the structure.

Supramolecular architectures :

In the solid state the mononuclear units of **1** pack into the supramolecular architecture through C–H...O/Cl hydrogen bonding (Fig. 2). The uniqueness of the present assembly is due to presence of two distinct interactive

zones with two different ranges of forces (Fig. 2). It is to be noted that the Mn2 centres are assembled with very strong H-bond, called zone A (2.10–2.51 Å) and Mn1 centres are within the weak range of H-bonding (2.52–2.58 Å), called zone B (Fig. 2). The coordinated *cisoid* ligand groups in the coordination environment of manganese(II) play important role by establishing double hydrogen bonding contacts with neighboring unit. The unique nature of each of the three nitrate anions plays decisive role to construct bi, tetra and hexa nodal H-bonds (Table 3). From the consideration of hydrogen bonding functionality each of these multi nodes is self-complementary and as a result a self-propagating supramolecular architecture results.

Bond Valence Sum calculation :

Bond Valence Sum (BVS), an empirical quantity, has been used to determine the oxidation state of each Mn in **1** in solids from the crystallographically determined bond distance data. Bond valence (S) = $\exp [(R_0 - R_{ij})/B]$, oxidation state = Σ bond valences; R_{ij} is the observed bond length, the usual procedure is to assume an oxidation state and to use previously determined R_0 values appropriate to the bond being considered¹². The constant B is determined as 0.37 (Table 4). Assuming both the Mn ions is in +III oxidation state we consider R_0 for Mn-O and Mn-N are 1.760 and 1.832 Å, respectively. The BVS found as 1.897 for Mn1 and 1.911 for Mn2. Again, considering Mn ions in +II oxidation state, R_0 is taken for Mn-O and Mn-N are 1.790 and 1.862 Å, respectively. Here, the oxidation levels for both the manganese ions have been assigned as 2.056 for Mn1 and 2.045 for Mn2. Thus the oxidation state for Mn1 and Mn2 in two asymmetric units of lattice **1** has been assigned as +II.

DNA binding studies :

Spectrophotometric titration :

Electronic absorption spectroscopy is an effective method to determine the binding mode of metal complex with DNA. To examine the binding mode of manganese(II) complex with DNA, the absorption spectra of complex **1** was recorded during the titration with CT-DNA. As shown in Fig. 3, the spectra indicate a significant hypochromism effect centered at 268 absorption maximum, which suggests that the complex interact with CT-DNA through an intercalative association in which the planar phenanthroline

Fig. 2. Construction of supramolecular network in zone A (Mn²⁺'s) and zone B (Mn¹⁺'s) using different range of forces (C-H...O/Cl interactions).

moieties slide between the CT-DNA base pairs by means of π - π stacking interactions¹³. In general, the observation of hypochromism is associated with the binding of the metal complex to DNA helix, due to the intercalative mode involving a strong stacking interaction between the aromatic chromophore of complex and the base pairs of DNA¹⁴. The binding constants, K_b for the complex **1** has been determined from the plot of $[DNA]/(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_f)$ vs $[DNA]$ and found to be $9.11 (\pm 0.2) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.9971$ for five points) (Fig. 3). The observed value of the binding constant is more in keeping with the intercalation binding of both the Mn^{II} complex with DNA.

Spectrofluorimetric titration :

Ethidium bromide (EB) can emit intense fluorescence in presence of DNA due to the strong intercalation be-

tween the adjacent DNA base pairs. The fluorescent light of EB-DNA system can be quenched by addition of the second agent, since it interacts with DNA and replaces the EB molecules. The quenching degree of fluorescence for EB-DNA system is usually used to determine the binding extent of the agent and DNA¹⁵. The addition of the cobalt complexes to DNA pretreated with EB causes an appreciable reduction in the fluorescence intensity (Fig. 4), indicating that complex **1** competes with EB to bind with DNA. The reduction of the emission intensity gives a measure of the DNA binding propensity of the complex and stacking interaction (intercalation) between adjacent DNA base pairs. Here, for complex **1**, a significant decrease of the fluorescence intensity of EB bound to DNA at 620–628 nm were recorded by increasing the concen-

Fig. 3. Changes in the electronic absorption spectra of **1** with increasing concentrations of CT-DNA; the inset shows a fitting of the absorbance data at 268 nm for **1** used to obtain binding constant, $K_b = 9.11 (\pm 0.2) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.9971$ for five points).

Table 3. Geometrical parameters of C/O-H...O/Cl hydrogen bonds (Å, °) involved in the supramolecular construction in complex **1**. D = donor, A = acceptor

D-H...A	D-H	H...A	D...A	D-H...A
O15-H15...O10 ^a	0.82	2.10	2.894(5)	162
O87-H87...C11 ^b	0.82	2.37	3.123(3)	152
C36-H36...O12	0.93	2.36	3.244(5)	159
C44-H44...O11 ^c	0.93	2.39	3.170(7)	142
C22-H22...O2 ^d	0.93	2.42	3.238(7)	147
C50-H50...O10 ^e	0.93	2.45	3.199(7)	138
C54-H54...O11 ^f	0.93	2.48	3.205(5)	136
C17-H17...O1	0.93	2.49	3.341(6)	152
C26-H26...O12 ^g	0.93	2.52	3.436(6)	170
C2-H2...O7	0.93	2.53	3.382(8)	153
C5-H5...O11 ^a	0.93	2.53	3.168(6)	126
C10-H10...O6	0.93	2.56	3.422(8)	154
C25-H25...O5 ^h	0.93	2.56	3.294(6)	136
C14-H14...O5 ^h	0.93	2.57	3.384(7)	146
C19-H19...O16	0.93	2.74	3.279(5)	118

Symmetry code : a = x, 1+y, z; b = x, -1+y, z; c = -x, 1/2+y, 1-z; d = -1+x, y, z; e = 1-x, 1/2+y, 1-z; f = 1+x, 1+y, z; g = 1-x, 1/2+y, 2-z; h = 1+x, y, z.

tration of the complexes (Fig. 4). The quenching of EB bound to DNA by the Mn^{II} complexes is in agreement with the linear Stern-Volmer equation :

$$I_0/I = 1 + K_{sv} [\text{complex}] \quad (2)$$

Table 4. Assignment of oxidation state of Mn ions and oxygen atom of water molecules

Atom	BVS	Assgt
Mn1	2.056	+II
Mn2	2.045	+II
O15	0.3420	Neutral O (from H ₂ O)
O16	0.3883	Neutral O (from H ₂ O)
O87	0.3248	Neutral O (from H ₂ O)

where I_0 and I represent the fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of quencher, respectively. K_{sv} is the linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant and [complex] the concentration of the quencher. From the slope of the regression line in the derived plot of I_0/I versus [complex] (Fig. 4), the K_{sv} value for **1** was found to be $K_{sv} = 5.8 (\pm 0.3) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$; ($R = 0.9923$ for five points) indicating a strong affinity of the complex to CT-DNA.

Conclusion :

We have synthesized and X-ray crystallographically characterized one new manganese(II)-phenanthroline complex. Crystalline architecture of the compound is also investigated. The oxidation states of the manganese ions have been determined by bond valence sum calculation. Binding of the mononuclear manganese(II) complex to CT-DNA have been investigated by electronic absorption

Fig. 4. (a) Emission spectra of the CT-DNA-EB system in tris-HCl buffer based on the titration of **1**. $k_{ex} = 522$ nm; the arrow indicates the increase of the complex concentration. (b) Plot of I_0/I vs [complex] for the titration of CT-DNA-EB system with **1** using spectrofluorimeter; linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant, $K_{sv} = 5.8 (\pm 0.3) \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.9923$ for five points).

titrations and fluorescence spectroscopic titration suggesting that the complex bind to DNA in an intercalative binding mode.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity 1,10-phenanthroline (Lancaster, UK), ammonium ceric nitrate (Aldrich, UK), manganese(II) chloride tetrahydrate (E. Merck, India), glacial acetic acid (E. Merck, India) were purchased from respective concerns and used as received. Calf thymus DNA (CT-DNA) was purchased from Sigma Aldrich, Germany. The DNA quality and integrity were evaluated using pulsed field gel electrophoresis and visualization after ethidium bromide (EB) staining. All the other reagents and solvents are of analytical grade (A.R. grade) and were purchased from commercial sources and used as received.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectrum was recorded (KBr discs, $4000\text{--}300 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) using a Perkin-Elmer RX1 FTIR spectrometer. Ground state absorption was measured with a JASCO V-530 UV-Vis spectrophotometer. The fluorescence spectra were recorded on the Fluorometer Hitachi-2000.

Synthesis of $[[\text{Mn}(\text{phen})_2(\text{OH})_2]_2[\text{Mn}(\text{phen})_2(\text{OH})_2\text{Cl}](\text{NO}_3)_3$ (**1**) :

Compound **1** was prepared by dropwise addition of methanolic solution (10 ml) of phen (0.396 g, 2 mmol) into a solution of $\text{MnCl}_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.197 g, 1 mmol) in methanolic solution of saturated sodium acetate (20 ml) keeping the solution on magnetic stirrer with slow stirring (450 rpm). Then solid ACN (550 mg, 1 mmol) was added portionwise into the pink solution and stirring continued to 30 min more. The pink solution was turned into brown and the supernatant liquid was kept in air for slow evaporation. After 7–10 days the fine microcrystalline compound **1** was separated out and washed in hexane and dried *in vacuo* over silica gel indicator. The spectroscopic measurements and elemental analyses confirm the structural formation of the complex.

Yield : (based on metal salt) 0.164 g (83.2%) (Found : C, 52.05; H, 3.03; N, 13.98. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{48}\text{H}_{34}\text{N}_{11}\text{ClO}_{12}\text{Mn}_2$ (**1**) : C, 52.16; H, 3.10; N, 13.94%); selected IR bands (KBr pellet, cm^{-1}) : 3418(s), 1588(s), 1384(s); UV-Vis (λ , nm) : 236, 268.

X-Ray crystallography :

Single crystal data of **1** were collected on a Bruker AXS KAPPA APEX II CCD DUO diffractometer using $\text{MoK}\alpha$ radiation ($k = 0.71073 \text{ \AA}$) at 296(2) K. Systematically absent reflections led to the identification of space

group P21(4) for **1**. Of the 37879 total reflections for the complex, 13683 with ($I > 2\sigma(I)$) were used for structure solutions. The structures were solved by direct methods, and the structure solution and refinement were based on $|F_2|$. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters whereas hydrogen atoms were placed in calculated positions where possible and given isotropic U values 1.2 times that of the atom to which they are bonded. The final differences Fourier map showed the maximum and minimum peak heights at +0.70 and $-1.14 \text{ e}\text{\AA}^{-3}$ for **1** with no chemical significance. All calculations were carried out using SHELXL-97¹⁶ and ORTEP-32¹⁷. The crystal data and data collection parameters are listed in Table 1.

Supplementary data :

CCDC 826170 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for **1**. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

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References

- (a) D. S. Sigman, T. W. Bruice, A. Mazumder and C. L. Sutton, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1993, **26**, 98; (b) J. K. Barton and A. M. Pyle, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1990, **38**, 413.
- (a) A. M. Burkhoff and T. D. Tullius, *Nature*, 1988, **331**, 455; (b) C. G. Riordan and P. J. Wei, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **116**, 2189.
- J. M. Kelly, M. J. Murphy, D. J. McConnell and C. OhUigin, *Nucleic Acids Res.*, 1985, **13**, 167.
- J. K. Barton, *Science*, 1986, **233**, 727.
- N. J. Turro, J. K. Barton and D. A. Tomalia, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1991, **24**, 332.
- K. C. Nicolau, P. Maligres, J. Shin, E. de Leon and D. Rideout, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **114**, 7825.
- (a) J. D. Tan, S. E. Hudson, S. J. Brown, M. M. Olmsted and P. K. Mascharak, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1992, **114**, 3841; (b) K. Nagai, B. J. Carter, J. Xu and S. M. Hecht, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1991, **113**, 5099.
- N. Armaroli, *Chem. Soc. Rev.*, 2001, **30**, 113.
- D. V. Scaltrito, D. W. Thompson, J. A. O'Callaghan and G. J. Meyer, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2000, **208**, 243.
- J. Bossert and C. Daniel, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2008, **252**, 2493.
- (a) K. Nakamoto, John Wiley & Sons Inc, New York, 1997; (b) S. Barbara, Wiley, New York, 2004.
- (a) H. H. Thorp, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1992, **31**, 1585; (b) P. L. Roulhac and G. J. Palenik, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2003, **42**, 118; (c) B. Biswas, A. Pal, P. Mitra, F. Tuna, M. Mukherjee and R. Ghosh, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2012, **65**, 4067.
- S. Tabassum, S. Parveen and F. Arjmand, *Acta Biomater.*, 2005, **1**, 677.
- (a) E. C. Long and J. K. Barton, *Acc. Chem. Res.*, 1990, **23**, 271; (b) S. Satyanaryana, J. C. Dabrowiak and J. B. Chaires, *Biochemistry*, 1993, **32**, 2573.
- (a) R. F. Pasternack, E. J. Gibbs and J. J. Villafranca, *Biochemistry*, 1983, **22**, 2406; (b) B. C. Baguley and M. LeBret, *Biochemistry*, 1984, **23**, 937.
- SHELXTL 5.10, Bruker Analytical X-Ray Instruments Inc, Karlsruhe, Germany, 1997.
- L. J. Farrugia, *J. Appl. Crystallogr.*, 1997, **30**, 565.

